

Remediation of cadmium from soil by surfactant Triton X-100

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Abstract : This study focuses on batch experiments conducted to evaluate the potential of surfactant Triton X-100 to remove heavy metals from artificially contaminated silt soil. Sorption experiments were carried out by varying concentration of cadmium and pH on soil samples. The soil samples selected for decontamination study were artificially contaminated with 500 mg L⁻¹ cadmium solutions at pH 4 and 7. Non-ionic surfactant Triton X-100 was used to decontaminate the soil at different time intervals. In sorption experiments variation of cadmium remaining with different time intervals was non-linear. It was found that maximum sorption of cadmium occurs at pH 7. Sorption continues till day 10. In desorption of 500 mg L⁻¹ cadmium contaminated soil, maximum desorption occurs at pH 4. The decontamination efficiency range of surfactant for soil contaminated with 500 mg L⁻¹ of cadmium was found to vary from 63.7% to 75.5% depending on pH.

Keywords : Surfactant, heavy metals, cadmium, contamination, sorption, desorption.

Introduction

Recent literature have shown that soil irrigation with water containing industrial effluent in big as well as in smaller areas are highly polluted with heavy metals including cadmium and requires a clean-up operation¹. Soils are described as sinks for metals. The latter being immobile in soil, accumulate in the topsoil, thus endangering the crops and vegetables and micro flora due to their toxic nature. The direct effect of Cd, Cu, Zn and Pb on soil microorganisms are well known^{2,3}. Heavy metals have a harmful effect on human physiology and other biological systems when they exceed the tolerance levels⁴. In recent years several studies have shown that metal such as cadmium, damage plant metabolism, causes reduction of growth, interferes with nutrient uptake⁵⁻⁷. Traditional treatment technologies for lead⁸ and cadmium contaminated soil have several inherent disadvantages because they cannot completely remove hazardous contaminants.

Soil washing with surfactant has recently become a useful and convenient technique for remediation of soil contaminated with heavy metals. Soil washing and flushing are the most common innovative technologies used to remove metals at superfund sites⁹. Castles¹⁰ and his co-worker developed a mobile soil washing system for the

use at super-vented sites which includes the possible use of surfactant. Nash *et al.* carried out small scale field trial of surfactant flushing at Air National Guard Base, Wisconsin¹¹. Remediation of arsenic and cadmium from artificially contaminated soil using surfactants are reported^{12,13}.

In the present work, various aspects including effect of time and metal concentration on sorption and desorption of cadmium on silt soil surfaces have been studied through batch experiment, to understand the remediation of cadmium from soil.

Results and discussion

The percent sorption of cadmium, by soil was calculated by using the equation,

$$\%R = \frac{C_i - C_e}{C_i} \times 100$$

where, R is removal of metal, C_i is initial concentration of metal ion in solution and C_e is equilibrium concentration of metal ion in solution.

The surfactant Triton X-100 was evaluated as a potential alternative for remediation for metal-contaminated soil¹⁴. The sorption and desorption experiments were conducted for cadmium on silt soil and the remaining cad-

mium in supernated solution was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The cadmium concentration was taken as 500 mg L⁻¹, 1000 mg L⁻¹, 1500 mg L⁻¹ and 2000 mg L⁻¹ for silt soil samples with different time interval at pH 4 and 7 for sorption studies. It was found that the variation of cadmium remaining with different time interval was non-linear in sorption. It has been observed that with in 10 days values of sorption varies which shows that no equilibrium was attained. Most of the mobilization occurs in 7 to 8 days. After that, a minor reduction in cadmium concentration was observed.

pH plays a very important role in sorption process. Soil pH is known to significantly affect the sorption process and leaching potential of the soil. Maximum sorption at same concentration occurred at pH 7. It means that for the same day and at similar concentration, sorption was dependent on pH. This shows that sorption increased with increase in pH. Percent sorption of cadmium onto soil and desorption by using surfactant at pH 4 were 75.5% and 75.5% respectively and at pH 7 were 94.5% and 63.7% respectively for 500 mg L⁻¹ of cadmium.

Desorption of the cadmium from soil by using surfactant Triton X-100 shows that at pH 7, there is decrease in the desorption of cadmium. In the desorption process, it was observed that maximum decontamination of cadmium occurs at pH 4 for 500 mg L⁻¹ concentration within 7 days and after that reaches equilibrium.

Experimental

The experiments were conducted on silt soil samples collected from 1.5 m depth, grounded properly by breaking heavy mass into finer particles, making it uniform and sieving through 425 μ sieve. The aqueous solution of various concentration of cadmium was prepared by dissolving pure cadmium chloride (Qualigens) in distilled water; pH of the solution was adjusted by appropriate acid and base. Four different concentrations of cadmium 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000 mg L⁻¹ was taken for studies through batch process at pH 4 and 7. The pH selected was for mixture of soil and cadmium. The reason for selecting these pH values is because of the fact that metal ions tend to get hydrolysed at higher pH. Moreover, it is easy to fix pH 4 and pH 7 using appropriate buffer solutions.

Conducting sorption experiments :

Equal quantity (about 50 g) of soil was filled in 40, 300 mL poly-ethylene bottles, for mixing at different time interval (day 1 to day 10) at pH 4 and 7. After that

known a quantity (500 mg L⁻¹) of cadmium solution was prepared separately thereby making the solution of soil and aqueous solution of cadmium (1 : 4 ratio) into each bottle for sorption studies. The time interval slip was pasted onto each bottle. The bottles were shaken manually for 30–40 s and kept still for 24 h and the residual cadmium concentration was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (ECIL-4141, Hyderabad). Similar experiments were also conducted for 1000 mg L⁻¹, 1500 mg L⁻¹ and 2000 mg L⁻¹ of cadmium at pH 4 and 7 and the whole process was repeated.

Conducting desorption experiments :

500 mg L⁻¹ of cadmium of day 10 at pH 4 and 7 were taken for study. A non-ionic surfactant Triton X-100 was used for decontamination phenomenon. The studies were carried out by aqueous surfactant solution, concentration 0.2% v/v at different time intervals (day 1 to day 10). Soil contamination with 500 mg L⁻¹ of cadmium concentration of day 10 at pH 4 and 7 were centrifuged, filtered and dried in room temperature. The dried soil sample was taken for desorption study. Desorption process was followed exactly as conducted in sorption experiments.

Conclusion :

The various aspects of cadmium sorption and desorption on silt soil surfaces have been studied through batch experiments to understand the problem of cadmium contamination on agricultural land and its remedial approaches. The overall studies using Triton X-100 suggests that the surfactant has a potential for the removal of cadmium for soil remediation. Based on the result of this study, it is expected that in a field study multiple washings should be given for the complete removal of cadmium.

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Note

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